

**THE TERMS OF EUPHEMISMS AND DYSPHEMISMS
AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION IN ENGLISH AND
UZBEK LANGUAGE**

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Annotation This article discusses about the terms of euphemism and dysphemism, their study and classification by English and Uzbek linguists. There are also ideas about the history of the origin of the terms euphemism and dysphemism.

Key words and expressions: euphemism, dysphemism, scholars, classification, origin, linguistics.

Annotatsiya Ushbu maqolada evfimizm va disfemizm atamalari, ularning ingliz va o'zbek tilshunoslari tomonidan o'rganib tasnif qilinganligi haqida so'z yuritiladi. Evfemizm va disfemizm atamalarning kelib chiqish tarixi haqida ham fikrlar keltiriladi.

Tayanch so'z va iboralar: evfemizm, disfemizm, olimlar, tasnifi, kelib chiqishi, tilshunoslik.

Аннотация В данной статье говорится о терминах эвфемизм и дисфемизм, их изучении и классификации английскими и узбекскими лингвистами. Существуют также представления об истории происхождения терминов эвфемизм и дисфемизм.

Ключевые слова и выражения: эвфемизм, дисфемизм, учёные, классификация, происхождение, лингвистика.

Nowadays we can see new kinds of terms in modern linguistics. One of them is euphemism. The term “euphemism” is derived from the Greek language “euphemismos” “eu” means good, “phemi” means I speak. In the dictionary of

“Lingvistik terminlar izohli lug‘ati” by A.Khojiyev, the meaning of this word is given as “an emotionally neutral word and expression that is used instead of words and expressions that are rude and uncomfortable in the eyes of the speaker”.

The English scholar A.A. Reformatsky states “euphemisms as words that are allowed to be used instead of prohibited (tabulated) words.”

When we speak about the classification of the word “euphemism”, we can see the numbers of classification types by different scholars. For instance, the linguist E.P. Senichkina distinguishes the following categories: euphemisms that have their own pattern in the language and are known to the speaker, the origin of which is unknown to the speaker (related to a person or an event) euphemisms, as well as historical euphemisms and dysphemisms.

According to A.M. Katsev’s research, euphemisms can be classified into 10 topics:

- 1) the name of divine forces;
- 2) units representing death and illness;
- 3) names related to the defect;
- 4) names related to gender;
- 5) names meaning poverty;
- 6) names denoting certain professions;
- 7) names of mental and physical disabilities;
- 8) names of parts of clothing.

Furthermore, social classification has great influence on revealing the meaning of euphemisms. It is distinguished on the basis of belonging to a certain social group.

The classification of B.A. Larin can prove these statement:

- 1) national, literary euphemisms;
- 2) class and professional euphemisms;
- 3) family and household euphemisms.

Linguistic classification of euphemisms was also carried out by some researchers:

- 1) according to its structure (word, phrase, sentence);
- 2) according to its methodological characteristics (high, neutral, low level);
- 3) according to word construction: a) based on displacement (metaphor, metonymy, narrowing of essence, etc.); b) created by changing the form (phonetic distortion, conversion, affixation, abbreviation, etc.); c) on the basis of appropriate units.

The next term is called dysphemism, and it is the substitution of a more offensive or disparaging word or phrase for one considered less offensive. Dysphemism can be used as opposite of euphemism. The word dysphemism is derived from the Greek word dys, means “miss,” or “none,” and pHEME, which means “reputation,” or “speech.” The real meaning of this word is a figure of speech that is defined as the use of disparaging or offensive expressions instead of inoffensive ones. Dysphemism is the use of negative expressions instead of positive ones. Throughout this term, a speaker can use them to humiliate or reduce the disapproved person or character.

Dysphemization is the “deterioration” of the meaning of a word, obtaining a negative, derogatory, rude, vulgar connotation.

Dysphemisms can be:

- such expressions and phrases, the impact of which on the listener (reader) or audience is shocking, offensive, and in some cases degrading;
- socially marked expressive vocabulary of varying degrees of sealing with a cultural component;
- a layer of expressive socially marked vocabulary of an already existing natural language.

Undoubtedly, dysphemization in the past and in the modern world has a different cognitive basis. Nowadays in modern linguistics, lexical units that primarily denote physical and mental disabilities, human defects, physiological functions, as well as designations of race, are subject to dysphemization. Those areas of life that most of the community tries to avoid mentioning, i.e. in their internal

content, dysphemisms coincide with permanent euphemisms, while the external form of dysphemisms is in opposition to euphemisms.

References:

1. Nelyubin L.L. Explanatory dictionary of translation. 3rd ed., revised. M.: Flinta: Nauka, 2003. 320 pp.
2. O‘zbek tilida evfemizm va disfemizm: uslubiy qo‘llanma / X. Qodirova. – Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2022., 118-b
3. Gulmira A. THE CONCEPT OF “FEAR” AND ITS STUDY //Involta Scientific Journal. – 2022. –Т. 1. – №. 13. – С. 96-99
4. Neflyasheva I.A. Keywords and word-formation models of the modern discourse //The Bulletin of the Adyghe State University. Maikop, 2009. Issue 2. P. 183-189
5. Sotvoldiyevna, U. D., & Zafarjon, D. (2023). Turli Tillardagi O ‘Xshatishlar Tarjimasining Lingvomadaniy Xususiyatlari. Miasto Przyszłości, 31, 330-332.
6. Usmonova, D., & Samijonov, M. (2022). Interactive appointments of the idioms in English and their alternatives in Uzbek. Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research, 2(5), 536-543.
7. Усмонова, Д. С. (2019). Роль и особенность соматических фразеологизмов различных языков. Мировая наука, (9 (30)), 250-252.
8. Axmadaliyeva Gulmira / “Qo‘rquv” konsepti va uning o‘rganilishi // “ Involta” Innovation Scientific Journal,2022, 46-48 b
9. Satvoldiyevna, U. D. (2020). A typological analysis of body parts names in English as part of somatic phraseology. Проблемы современной науки и образования, (2 (147)), 32-34.